

Contrast enhancement of multiple tissues in MR brain images with reversibility

Hao-Tian Wu, Kaihan Zheng, Qi Huang, and Jiankun Hu, *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Contrast enhancement (CE) of magnetic resonance (MR) brain images is an important technique to bring out the tissue details for clinical diagnosis. Recently, a new form of image enhancement has been proposed to complete the task without any information loss. Specifically, all information required to restore the original image is reversibly hidden into the enhanced image. Moreover, several reversible algorithms are proposed with image segmentation so that the region of interest can be exclusively enhanced. However, with these algorithms, it is hard to properly enhance the tissues in MR brain images when they are relatively small or connected with each other. To address this issue, a hierarchical CE scheme is proposed for MR brain images with reversibility. Firstly, a deep convolution neural network is used to segment multiple tissue classes automatically. Then, the segmented tissues are individually analyzed to guide the CE procedure so that multiple tissue-enhanced images are generated, respectively. Compared with utilizing the background information to guide the CE procedure, better effects of tissue enhancement and visual quality are both obtained by using the hierarchical scheme. The numerical results obtained from MR brain images demonstrate the reversibility and adaptability of the proposed scheme for enhancement of interested tissues.

Index Terms—Medical image enhancement, reversible data hiding, image segmentation, magnetic resonance image.

EDICS Category: MSP-WAT

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) plays a key role in clinical diagnosis by using a magnetic field and radio waves to create detailed pictures of the brain or other organs (e.g., [1], [2]). One advantage of using MRI is that little harmful radiation is emitted to the bodies, but the resultant image may be with low contrast. Since it is not easy for a clinician to diagnose with the low-contrast images, it is helpful to increase the contrast of tissues in magnetic resonance (MR) images (e.g., [3]). Thus contrast enhancement (CE) is considered as an important preprocessing in medical image analysis.

Recently, a new procedure has been proposed to perform the task of image CE without information loss. By using the technique of reversible data hiding (RDH) (e.g., [4]-[16]), all information required to restore the original image is reversibly hidden into the enhanced image (e.g., [17]-[27]). Additionally, extra data such as patient and authentication information can be hidden in the enhanced image (e.g., [19], [21], [23], [27]) to

be extracted when needed. For instance, if a contrast-enhanced image is unsuitable for an application, the original image can be obtained to generate a new one. Compared with the reversible schemes for computed tomography images (e.g., [19], [21], [23]), there are few algorithms for MR images.

The first work that combines image CE with RDH is proposed in [17], but directly applying it to medical images does not produce satisfactory effects due to the monotonous background. To improve the visual quality after CE, the Otsu's method [28] is adopted in [19] for background segmentation in medical images so that the region of interest (ROI) may be specially enhanced. Although better performance is obtained by differentiating the bins in histogram equalization (HE), the scheme proposed in [19] has some limitations. Firstly, the Otsu's method segments an image into two parts according to an automatically calculated threshold but the segmentation is not always accurate, especially when the ROI region is relatively small or the image histogram is not subject to the bimodal distribution. In order to improve the accuracy, a user interaction based segmentation algorithm named Grabcut [29] is employed in [27]. As the ROI can be better segmented with the aid of user interactions, difficulties may arise when the ROI regions are connected with each other. Secondly, the algorithms in [19], [27] utilize the segmented background to guide the CE procedure but do not work well when the ROI contains the same pixel values as in the background.

In the literature, quite a few MR image segmentation methods have been proposed (e.g., [30], [31]). What we aim at is to help to pre-screen multiple tissues in MR images by proposing a hierarchical CE scheme. Specifically, a convolutional neural network (CNN) is adopted to perform tissue segmentation automatically so that multiple tissue classes can be enhanced individually. Different from the algorithms proposed in [19], [27], the principal grey-level values in each segmented tissue are identified and used to bring out the details. In particular, only the histogram bins of the principal values are labelled and equalized for data embedding. A flowchart of the proposed reversible CE scheme is illustrated in Fig. 1, whereby several tissue-enhanced images may be generated from the same MR image, respectively. The experimental results on a set of MR brain images have shown efficacy and applicability of our proposed scheme. The evaluation results demonstrate its superior performance in terms of CE effect and image visual quality by comparing with the algorithms in [19], [27].

In the next section, a procedure of RDH with CE will be introduced, followed by a new scheme for MR images. The experiments and evaluation results are presented in Section III. Finally, the concluding remarks are drawn in Section IV.

Hao-tian Wu, Kaihan Zheng and Qi Huang are all with South China University of Technology, School of Computer Science and Engineering, Guangzhou 510006, China. E-mail: wuht@scut.edu.cn, 201921042323@mail.scut.edu.cn, 201720140339@mail.scut.edu.cn

Jiankun Hu is with School of Engineering and Information Technology, the University of New South Wales, Australian Defence Force Academy, Canberra, Australia. E-mail: j.hu@adfa.edu.au.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of a scheme for reversible MR image enhancement.

II. SCHEME FOR REVERSIBLE MR IMAGE ENHANCEMENT

Before proposing a new scheme for MR images, a RDH-based enhancement procedure will be briefly introduced.

A. RDH-based Procedure for Image Enhancement

For reversible CE of a grey-level image, a RDH-based method is presented in [17]. Firstly, an image histogram is obtained by counting the number of every grey-level value. In the histogram, the highest two bins are found out and their values are denoted as p_L and p_R ($p_L < p_R$), respectively. By shifting the bins around the chosen bins outward, two empty bins are created so that each of the chosen bins may be expanded into two adjacent, respectively. Specifically, the histogram is modified by traversing all pixels in a given order and a pixel value p is changed to p' by

$$p' = \begin{cases} p - 1, & \text{if } p < p_L \\ p - b_i, & \text{if } p = p_L \\ p, & \text{if } p_L < p < p_R \\ p + b_i, & \text{if } p = p_R \\ p + 1, & \text{if } p > p_R \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Note that p is unchanged if it is between p_L and p_R . When $p < p_L$ or $p > p_R$, p is modified but no bit is embedded. For the i -th pixel with value p_L or p_R , the i -th bit value (0 or 1), which is denoted by b_i , is embedded by changing p to p' . After applying Eq. (1) to every pixel that is contained in the histogram, each of the chosen bins are expanded to two adjacent bins. After that, p_L and p_R need to be updated by finding them in the *modified* histogram. By iteratively modifying the histogram by applying Eq. (1), the effects of HE may be achieved while the original pixel values can be restored according to the recorded p_L and p_R values. The bounding pixel values (0 and 255 for a 8-bit pixel value) may be overflowed after histogram modification. To prevent the overflows, preprocessing needs to be performed to reserve S empty bins on each side of histogram before expanding S pairs of bins for HE. In [20], another RDH-based algorithm is proposed by shifting the histogram bins towards one direction at each time. Similarly, the effects of CE can be achieved by iteratively expanding the highest bin into two adjacent ones.

B. Proposed Scheme for Reversible MR Image Enhancement

Based on the aforementioned procedure, a hierarchical CE scheme is proposed for MR images according to the flowchart

Procedure 1: Hierarchical tissue enhancement

Input: MR image I , threshold R and parameter S

Output: Tissue-enhanced image I_c

Segment I into different tissues with the U-Net [32] and use R to identify the principal pixel values in each issue; Apply the preprocessing to I and record the changes; Calculate the histogram of the preprocessed image;

foreach segmented tissue do

Label the histogram bins of the principal pixel values;

while the no. of expanded bins is less than $2S-2$ **do**

Choose the highest two among the labelled bins;

Expand the chosen bins to embed the changes in preprocessing and the previously expanded bin values by applying Eq. (1) to all pixels;

Collect the LSB values of the last 16 pixels;

Calculate the histogram excluding the 16 pixels;

Choose the highest two among the labelled bins;

Embed the LSB values, S value and previously expanded bin values by histogram modification;

Generate the tissue-enhanced image I_c by overwriting the 16 LSB values with the last expanded bin values.

as shown in Fig. 1. Different from other reversible algorithms, the ROI regions in a MR image are individually analyzed to guide the procedure of CE so that several tissue-enhanced images can be generated from one MR image, respectively.

1) *Tissue Segmentation*: The ROI (e.g., tumors) in MR brain images usually exist in the tissues such as cerebellum and unmyelinated white matter. To recognize and segment different tissues, a CNN-based method is adopted to automatically divide a MR brain image into different areas by their tissue classes. For simplicity of implementation, we use the U-Net [32] as the segmentation module. U-Net is a classic image segmentation framework with 2D CNN, and it works with few training images to yield precise segmentation results.

2) *Hierarchical CE of Segmented Tissues*: In [19], [27], some bins in the histogram are excluded from being expanded. As the same pixel values may exist in both background and ROI, the interested regions may not be properly brought out. Besides, multiple ROI regions cannot be separately enhanced by applying the methods in [19]. To cope with these issues, a hierarchical CE scheme is proposed by calculating the percentage of every grey-level value in a segmented tissue to identify the principle ones. If the percentage of a grey-level value is over a threshold R , the corresponding histogram bin is eligible to be expanded for data embedding, while the rest bins can only be shifted in HE. Since the histogram bins to be equalized are chosen according to each tissue to be enhanced, multiple tissue-enhanced images can be generated by enhancing every segmented tissue individually.

3) *Procedure of Hierarchical Tissue Enhancement*: The process of tissue CE is presented in Procedure 1 by expanding S pairs of histogram bins so that a tissue-enhanced image I_c is generated from a MR image I . The preprocessing proposed in [24] is adopted, which shrinks the histogram while preserving

Procedure 2: Recovering original MR image

Input: Tissue-enhanced image I_c

Output: Original MR image I

Collect the LSB values of the last 16 pixels in I_c to obtain the last expanded bin values (i.e., p_{LL} and p_{LR}); Calculate an image histogram excluding the 16 pixels; Apply Eq. (2) to extract the data hidden in the histogram and use Eq. (3) to restore the pixel values; Obtain the original LSB values, value of parameter S and previously expanded bin values from the extracted data; Write the original LSB values back to the 16 pixels; Calculate an image histogram including the 16 pixels; **while** less than S pairs of bin values have been used **do**
 Apply Eq. (2) to extract the data hidden in the histogram and use Eq. (3) to restore the pixel values;
 Obtain the previously expanded bin values from the extracted data and recalculate the histogram;
Obtain the recorded changes from the extracted data and reverse the preprocessing to recover I .

the order of all pixel values to avoid visual distortions. Note that the least significant bit (LSB) of sixteen pixels are used to save the last two expanded bin values represented in sixteen bits. For simplicity of understanding, the last sixteen pixels are chosen in Procedure 1, which positions can also be randomly chosen with a secret key. Since the LSB is overwritten only once, no visual pattern will be caused. The value of S is required to recover I from I_c , while neither the segmentation information nor the value of R is needed for image recovery.

4) *Recovery of Original Image:* To extract the hidden data, the values of the lastly expanded bins should be known, which are denoted by p_{LL} and p_{LR} , respectively. Then the pixels in a tissue-enhanced image are traversed to find those values equal to any of $\{p_{LL} - 1, p_{LL}, p_{LR}, p_{LR} + 1\}$. A bit value denoted by b' may be obtained from a pixel value p' by

$$b' = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when } p' = p_{LL} - 1 \text{ or } p' = p_{LR} + 1 \\ 0, & \text{when } p' = p_{LL} \text{ or } p' = p_{LR} \\ \text{null}, & \text{other cases} \end{cases}. \quad (2)$$

Meanwhile, a new pixel value p is generated to replace p' by

$$p = \begin{cases} p' + 1, & \text{when } p' < p_{LL} \\ p', & \text{when } p_{LL} - 1 < p' < p_{LR} + 1 \\ p' - 1, & \text{when } p' > p_{LR} \end{cases}. \quad (3)$$

By collecting the extracted bits, the value of S and those of the previously expanded bins can be known. The preprocessed image can be obtained by updating the values of $\{p_{LL}, p_{LR}\}$ in Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) for $S-1$ times. The process of data extraction and image recovery is summarized in Procedure 2.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We applied the proposed scheme and the schemes in [19], [27] to a set of 50 MR brain images, which were downloaded from the NeoBrainS12 challenge website [33]. Each of the test images was associated with a fully annotated ground truth segmentation map of tissue classes.

(a) Original (b) Otsu [28] (c) Ground truth (d) U-Net[32]

Fig. 2. A MR brain image and segmentation results.

A. Tissue Segmentation

When applying the proposed scheme, tissue segmentation was conducted by adopting the U-Net [32]. A set of 50 T2-weighted MR images at a resolution of 384×384 pixels were used as training data. For illustration, one test MR image and the results obtained with the U-Net [32] and Otsu's method [28] are shown in Fig. 2, respectively. Otsu's method may be applied to separate image background from the foreground, but cannot segment the individual tissue from the MR brain image. By adopting the U-Net, multiple tissues were automatically segmented from the MR images with high accuracy. Similar results were also obtained for other test images.

B. Visual Effects of CE and Reversibility

We compared the visual effects by setting parameters R and S to 0.01 and 40 in the proposed scheme and [19], [27], respectively. In applying the proposed scheme, the grey-level values whose percentages over 1% of the segmented tissue were labelled and the corresponding histogram bins were eligible to be expanded. In applying the schemes in [19], [27], the grey-level values whose percentages over 1% of the background were identified and the corresponding bins were excluded from being expanded in HE. In implementing each scheme, 40 pairs of bins were used for data embedding.

From the MR brain image in Fig. 2(a), multiple tissue-enhanced images were obtained with the proposed scheme, as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 for instances, where the enhanced tissues were identified according to the ground truth segmentation map and zoomed in the red box, respectively. When applying the scheme in [27], tissue segmentation was conducted by manually selecting the background and ROI region. When the tissues to be segmented are with small size, the background information used to guide the process of CE varied a little. The schemes in [19], [27] can only enhance all ROI regions at the same time so that only one contrast-enhanced image was generated from the original MR image.

As shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, each tissue in the original MR brain image can be adaptively enhanced with the proposed scheme. Compared with the scheme in [19], the details of each ROI were better brought out while better visual quality was obtained. Note that the visual effects could be tuned by adjusting the values of R and S , while the original MR image was correctly recovered from its enhanced versions.

C. Numerical Evaluation of Tissue Enhancement

To measure the effects of CE, relative entropy error (REE), relative contrast error (RCE) and relative mean brightness error

(a) Using the scheme in [19] (b) Using the proposed scheme

Fig. 3. Tissue-enhanced MR images with zoomed tissue ($S=40$ and $R=0.01$).

(a) Using the scheme in [19] (b) Using the proposed scheme

Fig. 4. Tissue-enhanced MR images with zoomed tissue ($S=40$ and $R=0.01$).

TABLE I
NUMERICAL RESULTS (MEAN) OBTAINED FROM FIVE MR BRAIN IMAGES
FOR THE TISSUE CLASS AS SHOWN IN FIG. 3.

Evaluation metric	R Scheme	2%	1%	0.2%	0.1%	2%	1%	0.2%	0.1%
		$S=30$				$S=40$			
RCEOI	Proposed	0.572	0.570	0.562	0.560	0.601	0.590	0.572	0.570
	[19]	0.510	0.518	0.550	0.551	0.514	0.510	0.563	0.564
	[27]	0.509	0.515	0.570	0.571	0.516	0.517	0.587	0.597
REEOI	Proposed	0.558	0.558	0.554	0.554	0.571	0.570	0.563	0.561
	[19]	0.517	0.527	0.553	0.553	0.522	0.519	0.558	0.559
	[27]	0.521	0.526	0.557	0.547	0.527	0.530	0.569	0.566
RMBEOI	Proposed	0.983	0.982	0.970	0.973	0.971	0.987	0.938	0.940
	[19]	0.895	0.909	0.952	0.953	0.862	0.882	0.922	0.923
	[27]	0.899	0.907	0.987	0.970	0.870	0.876	0.977	0.955
SSIM	Proposed	0.961	0.961	0.964	0.965	0.941	0.943	0.947	0.949
	[19]	0.896	0.935	0.946	0.945	0.873	0.860	0.911	0.909
	[27]	0.925	0.950	0.962	0.960	0.916	0.946	0.948	0.941
PSNR	Proposed	28.23	28.39	29.14	29.36	25.48	26.13	26.74	26.90
	[19]	23.94	26.01	28.94	28.70	22.04	22.32	25.95	25.84
	[27]	24.49	25.92	28.39	27.99	22.88	23.97	26.81	25.40
pure hiding rate	Proposed	0.141	0.148	0.160	0.164	0.108	0.123	0.151	0.157
	[19]	0.254	0.200	0.129	0.128	0.307	0.309	0.163	0.162
	[27]	0.264	0.230	0.138	0.114	0.285	0.252	0.110	0.062

TABLE II
NUMERICAL RESULTS (MEAN) OBTAINED FROM FIVE MR BRAIN IMAGES
FOR THE TISSUE CLASS AS SHOWN IN FIG. 4.

Evaluation metric	R Scheme	2%	1%	0.2%	0.1%	2%	1%	0.2%	0.1%
		$S=30$				$S=40$			
RCEOI	Proposed	0.569	0.560	0.548	0.541	0.596	0.577	0.566	0.557
	[19]	0.506	0.507	0.537	0.539	0.510	0.506	0.556	0.558
	[27]	0.503	0.507	0.553	0.497	0.506	0.507	0.568	0.495
REEOI	Proposed	0.549	0.544	0.540	0.537	0.564	0.560	0.552	0.547
	[19]	0.514	0.515	0.534	0.534	0.518	0.512	0.541	0.541
	[27]	0.517	0.520	0.534	0.499	0.517	0.517	0.547	0.492
RMBEOI	Proposed	0.985	0.989	0.993	0.990	0.972	0.972	0.987	0.990
	[19]	0.911	0.933	0.958	0.954	0.884	0.897	0.957	0.953
	[27]	0.914	0.929	0.971	0.942	0.892	0.900	0.975	0.912
SSIM	Proposed	0.961	0.963	0.966	0.968	0.943	0.948	0.952	0.955
	[19]	0.896	0.935	0.946	0.945	0.873	0.860	0.911	0.909
	[27]	0.925	0.951	0.969	0.991	0.916	0.946	0.958	0.982
PSNR	Proposed	27.71	28.09	28.79	29.41	25.06	25.54	26.14	26.61
	[19]	23.94	26.01	28.94	28.70	22.04	22.32	25.95	25.84
	[27]	24.49	26.03	28.47	31.97	22.88	24.07	26.46	28.40
pure hiding rate	Proposed	0.117	0.127	0.140	0.148	0.088	0.114	0.137	0.145
	[19]	0.254	0.200	0.129	0.128	0.307	0.309	0.163	0.162
	[27]	0.264	0.233	0.084	0.001	0.285	0.254	0.037	0.001

(RMBE) between the original and contrast-enhanced images defined in [34] were used. The peaked signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and Structural SIMilarity (SSIM) index [35] were also calculated between the original and contrast-enhanced images, while the RCE, REE and RMBE were calculated within each tissue by referring to the ground truth, respectively denoted by RCEOI, REEOI and RMBEOI. By applying the proposed scheme and [19], [27] with different S and R , the average numerical results were obtained from five MR brain images and listed in Table I and Table II, respectively. The pure data hiding rate included in comparisons is defined as the amount of bits embedded per pixel excluding those for image recovery.

The results in Table I and Table II show that the most CE effects were achieved with the proposed scheme because the largest mean REEOI, RCEOI and RMBEOI were obtained for the two tissue classes, respectively. The highest hiding rates were obtained with the scheme in [19] when $S=40$ but less CE effects were achieved. In general, the scheme in [27]

performed better with a smaller R but the obtained results were not as good as those achieved with the proposed scheme for a larger R . As the background information was used in applying the schemes in [19], [27], the enhancement effects varied a lot for different values of R , but the performance of the proposed scheme was stable and consistently good, indicating the better adaptability for tissue CE in MR brain images.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a hierarchical tissue enhancement scheme for MR images by adopting an efficient preprocessing. By employing the U-Net [32], tissues in MR brain images are segmented accurately and individually enhanced to bring out the details. The numerical results on a set of MR images have shown efficacy of analyzing each segmented tissue instead of using the background information in the reversible algorithms. In addition, reversibility and better adaptability have been obtained with the proposed scheme for tissue enhancement.

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